

SMARANDACHE - R - MODULE AND MORITA CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT. In this paper we introduced Smarandache - 2 - algebraic structure of R-Module namely Smarandache - R - Module. A Smarandache - 2 - algebraic structure on a set N means a weak algebraic structure A_0 on N such that there exist a proper subset M of N, which is embedded with a stronger algebraic structure A_1 , stronger algebraic structure means satisfying more axioms, by proper subset one understands a subset from the empty set, from the unit element if any, from the whole set. We define Smarandache - R - Module and obtain some of its characterization through S - algebra and Morita context. For basic concept we refer to Raul Padilla.

1. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 1.1. Let S be any field. An S-algebra A is an (R,R) - bimodule together with module morphisms : $\mu : A \otimes_R A \rightarrow A$ and $\eta : R \rightarrow A$ called multiplication and unit linear maps respectively, such that

$$\begin{aligned} A \otimes_R A \otimes_R A &\xrightarrow{\mu \otimes 1_A, 1_A \otimes \mu} A \otimes_R A \xrightarrow{\mu} A \text{ with } \mu \circ (\mu \otimes 1_A) = \mu \circ (1_A \otimes \mu) \text{ and} \\ R &\xrightarrow{\mu \otimes 1_A, 1_A \otimes \mu} A \otimes_R A \xrightarrow{\mu} A \text{ with } \mu \circ (\eta \otimes 1_A) = \mu \circ (1_A \otimes \eta) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1.2. Let A and B be S - algebras. Then $f : A \rightarrow B$ is an S - algebra homomorphism if $\mu_B(f \otimes f) = f \circ \mu_A$ and $f \circ \eta_A = \eta_B$

Definition 1.3. Let S be a commutative field 1_R and A an S - algebra M is said to be a left A - module.

If for a natural map $\pi : A \otimes_R M \xrightarrow{\otimes} M$, we have $\pi \circ (1_A \otimes \pi) = \pi \circ (\mu \otimes 1_M)$

Definition 1.4. Let S be a commutative field. An S coalgebra is an (R,R) - bimodule C, with R - linear maps

$\Delta : C \rightarrow C \otimes_R C$ and $\varepsilon : C \rightarrow R$, called comultiplication and counit respectively such that

$$\begin{aligned} C &\xrightarrow{\Delta} C \otimes_R C \xrightarrow{1_C \otimes \Delta, \Delta \otimes 1_C} C \otimes_R C \otimes_R C \\ &\text{with } (1_C \otimes \Delta) \circ \Delta = (\Delta \otimes 1_C) \circ \Delta \text{ and} \\ C &\xrightarrow{\Delta} C \otimes_R C \xrightarrow{1_C \otimes \varepsilon, \varepsilon \otimes 1_C} R \text{ with } (1_C \otimes \varepsilon) \circ \Delta = 1_C = (\Delta \otimes 1_C) \circ \Delta \end{aligned}$$

Definition 1.5. Let C and D be S - coalgebras. A coalgebra morphism $f : C \rightarrow D$ is a module morphism satisfies $\Delta_D \circ f = (f \otimes f) \circ \Delta_C$ and $\varepsilon_D \circ f = \varepsilon_C$

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Definition 1.6. Let A be an S - algebra and C an S - coalgebra . Then the convolution product is defined by

$f * g = \mu \circ (f \otimes g) \circ \Delta$ with $1_{Hom_R(C,A)} = \eta \circ \varepsilon(1_R)$ for all $f, g \in Hom_R(C, A)$ with for all

Definition 1.7. For a commutative field S an S - bialgebra B is an R - module which is an algebra (B, μ, η) and a coalgebra (B, Δ, ε) such that Δ and ε are algebra morphisms, or equivalently , μ and η are coalgebra morphism

Definition 1.8. Let R, S be fields M an (R,S) - bimodule. Then $M^* = Hom_R(M, R)$ is an (S, R) bimodule and for every left R - module L, There is a canonical module morphism.

$$\alpha_L^M : M^* \otimes_R L \rightarrow Hom_R(M, L)$$

defined by $\alpha_L^M : (m^* \otimes l)(m) = m^*(m)l$ for all $m \in M, m^* \in M^*$ and $l \in L$. If α_L^M is an isomorphism for each left R-module L. Then ${}^R M_S$ is called a Cauchy module.

Definition 1.9. Let R,S be fields with multiplicative identities , M an (S,R)-bimodule and N an (R,S) - bimodule.

Then the six-tuple datum. $K = [R, S, M, N, \langle, \rangle_R, \langle, \rangle_S]$ is said to be a Morita context if the maps $\langle, \rangle_R : N \otimes_S M \rightarrow R$ and $\langle, \rangle_S : M \otimes_R N \rightarrow S$ are bimodule morphisms satisfying the following associativity conditions :

$m' \langle n, m \rangle_R = \langle m', n \rangle_S m$ and $\langle n, m \rangle_R n' = n \langle m, n' \rangle_S, \langle, \rangle_R$ and \langle, \rangle_S are called the Morita maps.

2. CHARACTERISATION

Definition 2.1. The Smarandache R - module is defined to be an R - module R such that if there exist a proper subset A is an S - algebra with respect to the same induced operations on R.

Theorem 2.1. *Let A be S-coalgebra and Cauchy R-module iff A^* is an S-algebra*

Proof. Let us assume A^* is an S-algebra. Now to prove that A is an S-coalgebra .

we first check the counit conditions as follows. $\varepsilon : A \cong A \otimes_R S \xrightarrow{1_A \otimes \mu} A \otimes_R A^* \xrightarrow{\psi_A} R$

Next , We check comultiplication conditions as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta : A &\cong A \otimes_R S \otimes_R S \\ &\xrightarrow{1_A \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(A)} A \otimes_R (A^* \otimes_R A) \otimes_R A^* \\ &\xrightarrow{1_A \otimes A \otimes A^*} (A \otimes_R A) \otimes_R (A \otimes_R A)^* \\ &\xrightarrow{1_A \otimes R A} (A \otimes_R A) \otimes_R (A \otimes_R A)^* \\ &\xrightarrow{1_A \otimes A} (A \otimes_R A) \otimes_R A^* \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} (A \otimes_R A) \otimes_R A \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} A \otimes_R A \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} A \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow A$ is an S - coalgebra.

Conversely , Let us assume A is an S - coalgebra. Now to prove that A^* is an S - algebra . Now we first check the unit conditions as follows

$$\eta : R \xrightarrow{1_A \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(A)} A \otimes_R A^* \rightarrow 1_A \otimes A \xrightarrow{\cong} A$$

we check the multiplication conditions as follows A is a Cauchy module, We have $A \otimes_R A \rightarrow R$

$$A \cong A \otimes_R A \otimes_R R \xrightarrow{1_A \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(A)} A \otimes_R \otimes_R A^* \rightarrow R \otimes_R A^* \xrightarrow{\cong} A^*$$

$$\mu : A \otimes_R A \xrightarrow{\varepsilon \otimes 1_A} A^* \otimes_R A \xrightarrow{\cong} R \otimes_R A^* \xrightarrow{\cong} A^*$$

$\Rightarrow A^*$ is an S - algebra. \square

Theorem 2.2. *Let R be a R - module , if there exist a proper subset $\text{End}_S(M)^*$ of R Where S is a commutative field and M a Cauchy R - module. Then R is a smarandache R - module.*

Proof. Let us assume that R be a R - module.

Now to prove that $\text{End}_S(M)^*$ is an S - coalgebra which satisfies multiplication and unit conditions as follows.

$$\mu : \text{End}_S(M) \otimes_R \text{End}_S(M) \rightarrow \text{End}_S(M) \text{ and}$$

$$\eta : R \rightarrow \text{End}_S(M), \text{ We first check the comultiplication as follows.}$$

$$\Delta : \text{End}_S(M) \cong \text{End}_S(M) \otimes_R \xrightarrow{1_{\text{End}_S(M)} \otimes \eta} \text{End}_S(M) \otimes_R \text{End}_S(M)$$

Next , we check the counit conditions as follows.

$$\varepsilon : \text{End}_S(M) \cong \text{End}_S(M) \otimes_R R$$

$$\xrightarrow{1_{\text{End}_S(M)} \otimes \eta} \text{End}_S(M) \times_R \text{End}_S(M)$$

$$\xrightarrow{\cong \otimes \cong} \text{Hom}_R(M, M) \otimes_R \text{Hom}_R(M, M)$$

$$\xrightarrow{\cong \otimes \cong} (M^* \otimes_R M) \otimes_R (M^* \otimes_R M)$$

$$\xrightarrow{\psi_M \otimes \psi_M} R \otimes_R R$$

$$\xrightarrow{\cong} R$$

$\Rightarrow \text{End}_S(M)$ is an S - coalgebra. By theorem 2.1, $\text{End}_S(M)^*$ is an S - algebra .

\therefore By definition R is an smarandache - R - module. \square

Theorem 2.3. *Let R be a R - module , if there exist a proper subset $M \otimes_R M^*$ of R Where M is a Cauchy R - module. Then R is a smarandache R -module.*

Proof. Now to prove that $M \otimes_R M^*$ is an S - algebra . we check the multiplication and unit conditions as follows.

$$\mu : (M \otimes_R M^*) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R M^*) \xrightarrow{\cong} M \otimes_R (M^* \otimes_R M) \otimes_R M^*$$

$$\xrightarrow{1_M \psi_M \otimes 1_{M^*}} M \otimes_R R \otimes_R M^*$$

$$\xrightarrow{1_M \otimes \psi_M} R \otimes_R M^*$$

As M is a Cauchy module , we have

$$\eta : R \rightarrow \text{End}_S(M) \xrightarrow{\cong} M \otimes_R M^*$$

$\Rightarrow M \otimes_R M^*$ is an S - algebra.

\therefore By definition , R is an smarandache R - module. \square

Theorem 2.4. *Let R be a R - module, if there exist a proper subset the datum $[R, M, N, \langle \cdot \rangle_R]$ a morita context $(M \otimes_R N)$ of R is a S - algebra let S be a commutative field and M, N are Cauchy R - modules. Then R is a smarandache - R- module.*

Proof. Let us assume that R be a R-module. Now to prove that $M \otimes_R N$ is an S-algebra.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } \mu : (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) &\rightarrow M \otimes_R (N \otimes_R M) \otimes_R N \\ \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes \langle \cdot \rangle} \otimes 1_N} M \otimes_R R \otimes_R N \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} M \otimes_R N \end{aligned}$$

Which shows that the multiplication condition is satisfied. Also, since M and N are Cauchy R - modules, there exist maps

$$\begin{aligned} \eta : R &\cong R \otimes_R \xrightarrow{\eta \text{End}_S(M) \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(N)} (M^* \otimes_R M) \otimes_R (N^* \otimes_R N) \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong \otimes 1_{M \otimes N}} (M^* \otimes_R N^*) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong \otimes 1_{M \otimes N}} (M \otimes_R N)^* \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong \otimes 1_{M \otimes N}} R^* \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} R \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} (M \otimes_R N) \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow M \otimes_R N$ is an S - algebra.

\therefore By definition , R is an smarandache R - module. \square

Theorem 2.5. *Let R be a R - module , if there exist a proper subset datum $[R, M, N, \langle \cdot \rangle_R]$ a morita context $M \otimes_R N$ of R is a S - coalgebra let S be a commutative field, M, N are Cauchy R - modules. Then R is a smarandache R - module.*

Proof. Let us assume that R be a R - module .

Now to prove that $(M \otimes_R N)$ is an S - coalgebra.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta : M \otimes_R N &= (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (R \otimes_R R) \\ \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes N} \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(M) \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(N)} &(M^* \otimes_R M) \otimes_R (N^* \otimes_R N) \\ \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes N} \otimes \cong} &(M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M^* \otimes_R N^*) \\ \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes N} \otimes \cong} &(M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N)^* \\ \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes N} \otimes \langle \cdot \rangle_R^*} &(M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R R \\ &\xrightarrow{\cong} (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M \otimes_R N) \end{aligned}$$

Also we have the counit condition as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon : M \otimes_R N &\cong (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R R \xrightarrow{1_{M \otimes N} \otimes \eta \text{End}_S(M)} (M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R (M^* \otimes_R M) \\ \xrightarrow{\langle \cdot \rangle_R \otimes 1_{M^* \otimes M}} &R \otimes_R M^* \otimes_R M \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \xrightarrow{\cong} M^* \otimes_R M \\ \xrightarrow{\psi_M} R \end{array}$$

$\Rightarrow M \otimes_R N$ is an S - coalgebra.

By theorem $M \otimes_R N$ is an S - algebra

\therefore By definition , R is a smarandache R - module.

Hence the proof.

□

Theorem 2.6. *Let R be a R - module, Let S be a commutative field and M, N Cauchy R - Modules then the datum $[R, M, N, \langle \cdot \rangle_R]$ a morita context iff R is a smarandache R - module where $M \otimes_R N$ is a S - bialgebra, a proper subset of R.*

Proof. Part I : We assume that $M \otimes_R N$ is a S - bialgebra, a proper subset of R.

To prove that R is a smarandache R-module.

By theorem, $M \otimes_R N$ is a S - algebra and $M \otimes_R N$ is a S- coalgebra.

Hence $M \otimes_R N$ is a S - bialgebra. By definition, R is a smarandache R - module.

Part II : We assume that R is a smarandache R - module. To prove that $M \otimes_R N$ is a S - bialgebra. By known theorem assume that $M \otimes_R N$ is an S - bialgebra. Then we have the map.

$$\varepsilon = \langle \cdot \rangle_R : M \otimes_R N \rightarrow R$$

Associativity of the map $\varepsilon = \langle \cdot \rangle_R$ holds because the diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} M \otimes_R N) \otimes_R M & \xrightarrow{\cong} & M \otimes_R (N \otimes_R M) \\ \varepsilon \otimes 1_M \searrow & M & \swarrow 1_M \otimes \varepsilon \end{array}$$

is commutative. Hence the datum $[R, M, N, \langle \cdot \rangle_R]$ is a Morita context.

Hence the proof.

□

3. REFERENCES

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